

Effects of Farmers' Socio-economic Characteristics on Adoption of Push Pull Technology in Western Kenya: Insights from UPSCALE Project

Ng'ong'a, E.¹, Osewe, D. O.², Ombok, B³, Odhiambo, G⁴, Aila, F⁵, Kharde, P.B.⁶
and Waman, G.K.⁷

1 & 2. Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, School of Agriculture, Food Security and Environmental Sciences, Maseno University, Kenya.

3. Department of Accounting and Finance, School of Business and Economics, Maseno University, Kenya.

4. Department of Crop and Soil Sciences, School of Agriculture, Food Security and Environmental Sciences, Maseno University, Kenya

5. Department of Business Administration, School of Business and Economics, Maseno University, Kenya

6 & 7. Department of Extension Education, Mahatma Phule Agricultural University, Rahuri, Maharashtra, India

Corresponding author's e-mail: danosewe@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

*Agricultural technologies are being developed and improved to help in curbing constraints associated with agricultural production and income. Push pull Technology (PPT) is an organic approach in pest management that uses cereal as the main crop and companion crops as *Brachiaria.spp* and *desmodium.spp*. UPSCALING the benefits of PPT and its adoption has the potential for intensification of farming systems, addresses food security, livelihoods and climate change resilience in Kenya and beyond while reducing the environmental impact of agricultural practices. The technology significantly reduces Fall Army Worm (FAW), *Striga* weed and stem borer infestation which is still major menace to cereal yield losses in Kenya. Maize worth USD 1.5b is lost annually due to stem bore in Sub Saharan Africa (SSA). Maize is a staple food in East Africa. PPT enhances quality of grains, retains soil moisture, improves soil fertility and protects the soil from erosion thus has the potential to increase cereal yields by 25 per cent-30 per cent. This study was done in Western Kenya with a focus of determining the effects of farmers' socio-economic characteristics on adoption of PPT. Sample size of 304 maize household farmers from five counties with UPSCALE project were proportionately sampled. Questionnaires and key informant interviews (KII) were used for data collection. The findings revealed that *Striga* weeds, stem borer and fall army worms are still the major menaces. Farmers practiced PPT for various combined reasons which included; to control *striga*, to increase crop productivity and to control stem borer at 76.70 per cent, 59.09 per cent and 57.39 per cent respectively. The outstanding observation is that only a few farmers (3.41%) practiced PPT as a response to climate change. This could be due to labour intensification of the technology.*

Keywords: Farmer' Socio-Economic Characteristics, Adoption, Push Pull Technology, UPSCALE, Kenya

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural technologies are being developed and improved to help in curbing constraints associated with agricultural production and income. Adoption of agricultural technologies has the potential to contribute to sustainable farming systems and improves the global market. Kenya's International Centre of Insect Physiology

and Ecology (ICIPE) and Britain's Rothamsted Research collaborated with partners in Eastern Africa developed the Push-Pull technology (PPT). This is an organic approach in pest management that uses cereal the main crop and companion crops as *Brachiaria spp.* and *desmodium spp.* (Amudavi et al., 2009; Cook, et at. 2007).

According Mwangi and Karuki (2015) to

East African countries often experience major constraints such as food insufficiency, increasing population pressure on resources, declining food

production, high incidences of environmental unsustainability, as well as high food prices.

Maize is a staple food in western region of

Fig. 1. Maize field infested with Striga and stalk borer (Source: Amudavi, et al., 2009)

PPT is an innovative knowledge-based technology that significantly reduces fall armyworm (FAW), Striga weed and stem borer infestation which is significant to cereal yield losses in western region of the republic of Kenya (Figure 1). PPT enhances quality of grains, retains soil moisture, improves soil fertility and protects the soil

from erosion thus it has the potential to increase cereal yields by 25%-30% (Cheruiyot et al., 2022).

The technique involves intercropping silver leaf desmodium, a fodder legume, with maize, Napier and Sudan grass (Figure 2) to provide both immediate and long-term benefits. (Cheruiyot et al., 2022).

Fig. 2. Push Pull Technology (Source: <http://www.push-pull.net/works.shtml>)

PPT has a number of benefits that includes but not limited to stem borer and striga control; increased fodder production; nitrogen fixation and reduced soil erosion; increased forage seed

production; increased crop yields; improved dairy production; improved Farm Yard Manure (FYM) production; and increased household income as depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Benefits of Push Pull Technology

Upscale is a Horizon 2020 (H|2020) project focusing on increasing production efficiency of smallholder farmers in East Africa. The project applies transdisciplinary approaches to research and innovation through Multi-Actor Community (MAC) engagements which is likely to enable smallholder farmers cope with climatic changes while ensuring sustainability and resilience. It is an EU-funded project which aims at scaling up the understanding and applicability of push-pull technology from individual fields, farm, landscape and regional scales; and from cereal to other crops and cultivation systems.

METHODOLOGY

This study was done in Western Region of the Republic of Kenya. The focus of the study was to determine the effect of farmers' socio-economic characteristics on adoption of PPT. Sample size of 304 maize household farmers from counties with UPSCALE project were proportionately sampled namely Kisumu, Homa Bay, Vihiga and Siaya (Table 1). Questionnaires and key informant interviews (KII) were used for data collection (Kothari & Garg 2014).

Table 1
Sample Size Determination

County	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Kisumu	47	15.46
Homa Bay	62	20.39
Vihiga	75	24.67
Siaya	120	39.47
Total	304	100

This study employed a descriptive and casual research design that allows data collection from individuals from the five counties. This helps to compare relationships between two or more variables among different maize farmers among the UPSCALE project. The research designs were appropriate since the study tends to explore aspects of PPT adoption among smallholder maize farmers

as opined by Rodger (1995)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Farmers' Socio-Economic Characteristics Under UPSCALE Project

The results in Table 2 shows socio-economic characteristics of the respondents in the study area.

Table 2
Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Gender of respondent	Frequency		Percentage (%)	
Female	190		62.50	
Male	114		37.50	
Gender of Household head (HH)				
Female	83		27.30	
Male	221		72.70	
Marital status of HHH				
Single (never married)	1		0.33	
Married	222		73.03	
Separated	1		0.33	
Divorced	3		0.99	
Widowed	77		25.33	
Main occupation of HHH				
Agriculture self-employed	239		78.62	
Agriculture wage labour	3		0.99	
Non- Agri self-employed	29		9.54	
Non- Agri wage labour	6		1.97	
Retired/on pension	2		0.66	
Salaried worker	19		6.25	
Remittances	1		0.33	
Sickly/old/not able to work	1		0.33	
Unemployed	4		1.32	
	Mean	min	max	S. Dev.
Household head age (years)	55.82	23	90	12.8974
Academic Years	9.05	0	36	4.2095
Family size (number)	5.92	1	15	2.5486
No. of HH members earning income	1.42	0	9	1.0310
Agricultural Experience (years)	23.19	3	60	12.1106
Total land owned by the household (acres)	2.1625	0	20	2.4271
Total land Rented-in by the household (acres)	1.11	0.125	8	1.1580
Total land Rented-out by the household (acres)	0.97	0.25	2	0.6373

A total of 304 farmers were proportionately household heads were mostly within the prime sampled and interviewed from Kisumu, Homabay, productive age brackets with an average household Vihiga and Siaya Counties at 15.46 per cent, 20.39 per head being 55.82 years of age and 73.03 per cent of cent, 24.67 per cent and 39.47 per cent, respectively. them were married. The household heads were Individuals within the household who were more educated as most of them had acquired formal informed about the households' farming activities education with an average of 9.05 academic years. were chosen to be the respondents during the The statistics reflect high dependency since the interviews. Out of the sampled respondents, results showed that an average household had 5.92 majority (62.50%) were female. This result members of whom an average 1.42 members were in highlights the increased involvement and gender a position of earning income. role of women in the farming sector.

A large proportion of the interviewed interviewed farmers relied on agriculture as their households were male headed (72.70), the primary source of income, this was through being

agriculturally self-employed or through agriculture related wage. The sampled farmers were experienced farmers and this is depicted by their average 23.19 years of farming activities. On average the households owned 2.1625 acres of land which is relatively small given the mixed farming nature of the farmers in the study area, to expand on their farm land some rented in land which was averagely an addition of 1.11 acres. Some households other than

relying on agricultural production of their land, they earned income from it by renting it out, this was at an average of 0.97 acres of land rented out by a farmer.

Adoption of Push Pull Technology

Table 3 shows results on effects of farmers socio economic characteristics on adoption of push pull technology.

*Table 3
Effects of farmers socio economic characteristics on adoption of push pull technology*

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	
Is your household aware of/ heard about Push-pull technology (PPT)			
Yes	235	77.30	
No	69	22.70	
How did you first learn about PPT?			
ICIPE staff	175	74.47	
Research Centre (trials/demos/field days) KALRO, ICIPE, ISD, ICRAF, GIZ	39	16.60	
Government extension	5	2.13	
Farmer Coop/Union/group	7	2.98	
Farmer field school	5	2.13	
NGO/CBO	7	2.98	
Fellow farmer	44	18.72	
Universities	1	0.43	
Social media; YouTube/radio TV etc.	9	3.83	
Did the HH use PPT in the past?			
Yes	47	44.76	
No	58	55.24	
Is your household currently using PPT?			
Yes	130	44.68	
No	105	55.32	
Have you consistently used PPT?			
Yes	136	76.84	
No	41	23.16	
Will you continue using PPT in future?			
Yes	128	98.46	
No	2	1.54	
What are the reasons for using PPT			
Increase crop productivity only	104	59.09	
Increase livestock productivity only	38	21.59	
To increase livestock fodder	76	43.18	
Adopt to changing climate	6	3.41	
To improve soil fertility	84	47.73	
To control striga	135	76.70	
To control stem borer	101	57.39	
To control fall armyworm incidences	78	44.32	
	Mean	Min.	Max.
For how many years have you known PPT?	8.30	1	27
For how many years have you been using PPT?	8.32	1	25
How many farmers do you know who are using PPT in your village?	5.91	0	100

From the results in table 3, it's worth noting that the farmers' awareness of push-pull technologies in the study region is good, with 77.30 per cent reporting that they were aware or had heard of push-pull technologies while 22.70 per cent were not aware or had never heard of it. The average number of years that the farmers had known PPT and the years they had practiced it were very close as they were 8.30 years and 8.32 years respectively. The highest number of years reported that a farmer had practiced PPT was 25 years.

The farmers' awareness of the PPT was facilitated by a combination of different actors. ICIPE staff were the most influencers on PPT at 74.47 per cent, followed by influence of fellow farmers and Research Centre (trials/demos/field days) at 18.72 per cent and 16.60 per cent respectively. It is worth noting that even though the Universities had an influence in PPT awareness it was the least impactful at 0.43 per cent. From the results it can be noted that farmers were aware of other farmers PPT practices as the reported an average 5.91 neighboring farmers to be practicing it.

As at the time of conducting the study, 44.68 per cent of the farmers were practicing PPT while 55.32 per cent were not practicing PPT. 44.76 per cent of those who were not currently practicing PPT had previously in the past adopted it and later de-adapted it while, 55.24 per cent of those who were not practicing currently had never adopted it even before. Of the farmers who were currently practicing PPT 76.84 per cent had practiced it consistently over the past years. On the future prospect of PPT, 98.46 per cent of those who were currently practicing PPT reported that they will continue practicing it.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The farmers practiced PPT for various combined reasons which included; to control striga, to increase crop productivity only and to control stem borer reported at 76.70 per cent, 59.09 per cent and 57.39 per cent respectively. The outstanding observation is that only a few farmers (3.41%) practiced PPT as a response to climate change. This could have been due labour intensive nature of PPT.

Paper received on 26/06/2024

Accepted on 25/08/2024

REFERENCES

- Amudavi, D., Khan, Z., Wanyama, J., Midega, C., Pittchar, J., Hassanali, A., & Pickett, J. (2009). Evaluation of maize household farmers' field days as a dissemination tool for push-pull technology in Western Kenya. *Crop Protection*, 28, 225–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2008.10.008>.
- Cheruiyot, D., Chidawanyika, F., Midega, C. A. O., Pittchar, J. O., Pickett, J. A., & Khan, Z. R. (2022). Field evaluation of a new third generation push-pull technology for control of striga weed, stemborers, and fall armyworm in western Kenya. *Experimental Agriculture*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479721000260>
- Cook, S. M., Khan, Z. R., & Pickett, J. A. (2007). The use of push-pull strategies in integrated pest management. *In Annual Review of Entomology* (52, 375–400). <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ento.52.110405.091407>
- Kothari, C.R and G. Garg. 2014. *Research methodology: Methods and Techniques*. Third Edition. New Age International Publishers, New Delhi
- Kanampiu, F., Makumbi, D., Mageto, E., Omany, G., Waruingi, S., Musyoka, P., & Ransom, J. (2018). Assessment of Management Options on Striga Infestation and Maize Grain Yield in Kenya. *Weed Science*, 66, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1017/wsc.2018.4>
- Mwangi, M., & Kariuki, S. (2015). *Factors Determining Adoption of New Agricultural Technology by Smallholder Maize household farmers in Developing Countries*. *Issn*, 6(5), 2222–1700. www.iiste.org
- Rogers, E. M. (1995). *Diffusion of Innovations*. Free Press.

.....

Extension of Inclusive Education Practices in Nagaland: Reflections from Tribal School Teachers

Buno Liegise¹, Anu G. S.² and Khriebeizonuo Caroline³

1. Head, Department of Education, Nagaland University Kohima

2. Associate Professor Department of Education, Nagaland University Kohima

3. Research Scholar, Department of Education, Nagaland University, Kohima

Corresponding author's e-mail: anueducation@nagalanduniversity.ac.in

ABSTRACT

This article, titled 'Extension of Inclusive Education Practices in Nagaland: Reflections from Tribal School Teachers,' is an empirical study based on the primary data collection of twenty representative tribal schools in Nagaland. Nagaland is a small northeast state of India with rich, multi-cultural, and multilingual regions. The primary research focus of the study is to explore the reflections and perceptions of tribal school teachers about inclusive educational practices. The methodology used for the present research study is descriptive in nature, and the survey technique is used to collect the data. Teachers Perception of Inclusive Education Scale was used to collect data from 275 tribal teachers using a simple random sampling technique. The exploratory factor analysis (EFA) results indicate that teachers are generally positive and invested in inclusive education practices. However, they may need additional support, such as access to resources, collaboration opportunities, and professional development focused on differentiation and supporting diverse learners. The role of the teacher is critical to the success of inclusive education. Findings suggest that teachers may need additional support in areas such as access to resources, collaboration, and professional development focused on differentiation and diverse learners. Further research explores these connections and experiences through qualitative studies for the extension of the inclusive educational practices in Nagaland in particular and in North-East India in general.

Keywords: Extension, Inclusive Education, Tribal school, Nagaland

INTRODUCTION

Education is an essential instrument for achieving social justice and equality. It plays a vital role in promoting and achieving an inclusive and equitable society in which each and every child, irrespective of his/her ability and disability, has the right to learn, thrive and contribute to the development of the community. It is also regarded as a cornerstone in developing the potentialities of children, more so children with special needs. Inclusive education means the education of all, irrespective of their differences in background and abilities, by making necessary arrangements to adapt to the needs of every child. It aims to promote equal opportunity and provide quality education to all. The Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act 2016 defines inclusive education as a 'system of education wherein students with and without disabilities learn together, and the system of

teaching and learning is suitably adapted to meet the learning needs of different types of students with disabilities.'

Children with special needs have different needs that require special attention and services compared to other children and are often denied their rights due to their differences and lack of infrastructure and support resources. To ensure their full participation and inclusion in the school, it is necessary to provide appropriate accommodations and resources tailored to their needs and potential. Resources play a vital role in an inclusive classroom environment as they help to promote learning and support diverse needs. Barrier-free access, assistive devices, appropriate teaching-learning materials, technology-based tools, special educators, curriculum and co-curricular activities, vocational skills/education, appropriate resources, etc., must be made available

to help children with disabilities to be able to deal with their limitations, with his peers and teachers in the classroom.

The goal of inclusive education is to provide equal access to opportunity and participation to every child to enable them to reach their full potential and to prepare them for life with appropriate teaching and learning environments and resources. Inclusion reinforces the idea that uniqueness and differences are accepted and respected. Inclusion is equally important in promoting understanding, reducing social prejudice and strengthening social integration.

Reflections from Literature Review

Alam, *et al.* (2004) stressed the importance of creating an inclusive learning environment and appropriate approaches tailored according to the needs, limitations and requirements of students with exceptionalities. Kanmani (2023) concluded that technical aids and assistive equipment immensely enhance the teaching-learning process. In the context of an inclusive classroom, he further stressed the rehabilitative and adaptive aspects of technology. Khan & Behlol (2014) concluded that the accessibility of the school's infrastructure normally caters to the needs of all students, but the curriculum, teaching & learning aids, equipment, and assessment method need to be modified. It should cater to the needs of students with disabilities. He indicated that despite instruction to include students with disabilities in the mainstream, it was not up to expectation due to insufficient support resources. Simorangkir (2021) stated that not all-inclusive elementary schools have the facilities and infrastructure as per the rules and regulations of the government. Prayash & Vaishali (2022) opined that architectural facilities for Children with special needs were good on physical and teaching learning facilities; however, independent living facilities were on an average level for CWSN to include them in the mainstream. Each child with special needs has different types of needs for facilities and infrastructure based on their distinct disabilities. In addition, it was learnt that various infrastructure facilities could be prepared for other types of children with special needs

characteristics, such as rooms, equipment, media, and student learning resources (Azzahra *et al.*, 2022).

Significance of the study

India has witnessed the rise of the inclusive education movement, which aims to ensure that quality education is provided to all students regardless of their ability or background (Haug, 2017). It is essential to recognize that tribal schools in Nagaland play a vital role in the closing of educational inequalities, but the success of inclusive education depends on the attitudes and support of teachers (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022). This research article focuses on assessing the perceptions, attitudes, and knowledge of teachers regarding inclusive education in their school settings, as well as their understanding of current practices in the schools where their children are enrolled. Moreover, the report will also examine the opinions of teachers towards inclusive education, as well as any objections they may have about it. The specific objective of this study is to identify gaps in teachers' perceptions of inclusive education in Nagaland's tribal schools, develop customized strategies for addressing particular problems, and increase their participation in the study.

RESEARCH QUESTION

For Nagaland's tribal schools to be successful in developing an inclusive learning environment, it is essential to map out teachers' perspectives, and this will lay the foundation for a more successful implementation, enhancing the educational experiences of all learners. This survey aims to learn teachers' perceptions of inclusive education in tribal schools in Nagaland's Kohima and Dimapur districts. Hence, the research question of the present study is entitled:

How about teachers' perceptions of inclusive educational practices among the tribal schools in Nagaland with respect to the following factors?

- *Teacher Responsibility and Collaboration*
- *Teacher Self-Efficacy and Support*
- *Perceived Support for Inclusive Practices*
- *Teacher Confidence in Differentiation and Support*
- *Teacher Beliefs about Inclusive Education*

METHODOLOGY

The methodology used for the present research study is descriptive, and the survey technique is used to collect the data. Teachers Perception of Inclusive Education Scale was conducted in Nagaland with 275 tribal teachers (n=275). Using a simple random sampling approach (Thomas, 2022), 20 schools, ten each from the Kohima and Dimapur districts, were selected for this study. The data analysis employs a 5-point Likert scale and

exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to identify the underlying factors that impact teachers' involvement in inclusive education. To determine the most significant aspects of the Teacher's perception of the inclusive education (TPIE) model, the primary data was analysed using SPSS 26 (Statistical Package for Social Science).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data collected was analysed below based on the research question postulated for the study.

*Table 1
Teachers Perception Factor Analysis*

Factors (Cronbach Alpha)	Eigenvalue	Per cent of Variance	Loading
Factor 1(0.819): Teacher Responsibility and Collaboration	5.869	29.347	
Teachers believe they should be trained in inclusive education			0.82
Teachers see themselves as vital for inclusive education success			0.818
Creating a welcoming and inclusive environment is seen as a teacher's responsibility			0.804
Collaboration with other professionals is viewed as important			0.652
Factor 2(0.800): Teacher Self-Efficacy and Support	2.734	13.672	
Having access to resources and information for supporting students with disabilities			0.826
Ability to get support from other professionals			0.729
Feeling equipped with skills and knowledge			0.671
Familiarity with relevant policies and procedures			0.646
Factor 3(0.745): Perceived Support for Inclusive Practices	1.354	6.77	
Feeling supported by the school administration			0.764
Feeling supported by parents			0.740
Feeling supported by colleagues			0.672
Belief in inclusive education for social justice			0.509
Factor 4(0.685): Teacher Confidence in Differentiation and Support	1.151	5.756	
Confidence in creating a positive learning environment			0.783
Ability to modify instruction and assessments			0.749
Confidence in supporting all students			0.454
Factor 5(0.535): Teacher Beliefs about Inclusive Education	1.083	5.417	
Teacher role in tribal areas			0.662
Opportunities for inclusive education in tribal areas			0.637
Belief in benefits for all students			0.512
Belief in all students' right to quality education			0.436

A factor analysis of teachers' perceptions of inclusive education practices is presented in Table 1, which shows that five key factors account for more than 60% of the variance in teacher perceptions. The analysis shows no evidence of a problem with the model fit or overall reliability (alpha 0.861), which indicates that both the model and the data are reliable.

- **Factor 1 (Teacher Responsibility and Collaboration)** indicates the importance teachers place on their role in inclusive education. In addition to training (0.82 loadings), teachers emphasize their contribution (0.818 loadings) and value a positive environment. This element implies that educators prioritize inclusive practices but may require regular support and training.
- **Factor 2 (Teacher Self-Efficacy and Support)** is primarily concerned with the level of confidence and resources that teachers possess. Having the necessary resources and information (0.826 loading) along with support from other professionals (0.729 loading), is considered significant. Teachers should be provided with resources and opportunities to enhance their knowledge and skills in inclusive education practices.
- **Factor 3 (Perceived Support for Inclusive Practices)** explores how teachers perceive the support they receive from different parties. Feeling supported by administration (0.764 loadings), parents (0.740 loadings), and colleagues (0.672 loadings) is essential. Schools can promote inclusive practices by creating a collaborative environment where teachers feel supported by the administration, parents and colleagues.
- **Factor 4 (Teacher Confidence in Differentiation and Support)** focuses on teachers' confidence in creating inclusive learning environments and modifying instruction. The loading of 0.749 indicates that teachers are confident in their ability to create positive environments and modify

instruction/assessments. Support for diverse learners and promoting differentiated instruction may be advantageous for teachers.

- **Factor 5 (Teacher Beliefs about Inclusive Education)** concerns the broader notions of inclusive education held by teachers, particularly in tribal contexts (statements with lower loadings may not be pertinent for the general population) In these areas, teachers are aware of the importance of teaching in tribal contexts (0.662 loading) and recognize the potential benefits and opportunities of inclusive education (0.637 loading) It is possible that the survey could be expanded to include more questions that inquire about teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education.

CONCLUSION

The factor analysis of teachers' perception of inclusive education (IE) indicates that teachers are generally positive and invested in inclusive education practices. However, they may need additional support, such as access to resources, collaboration opportunities, and professional development focused on differentiation and supporting diverse learners. Future research could explore how these factors relate to actual inclusive education practices and qualitative studies to provide deeper insights.

This study examines teachers' perceptions of inclusive education practices using survey data collected from teachers. Five key factors account for the variance between these two outcomes: teacher collaboration and accountability, self-efficacy, perceived support for inclusive practices, confidence in differentiation and support, and beliefs about inclusive education. The role of the teacher is critical to the success of inclusive education. Training, creating an atmosphere that fosters collaboration, and providing a welcoming environment for students are all factors that teachers emphasize. It is also important to point out that students have access to resources and support from their school administration, parents, and teachers.

However, it may be necessary for them to increase professional development focused on their confidence in their ability to support all student differentiation and diverse learners. Further needs in the future. Teachers know their role in tribal research could explore these connections and their areas and recognize the potential benefits of experiences through qualitative studies to extend the inclusive education for all students. Findings inclusive educational practices in Nagaland in suggest that teachers may need additional support particular and in North-East India in general. in areas such as resource access, collaboration, and

Paper received on 12/07/2024

Accepted on 08/09/2024

REFERENCES

- Alam, N., Bhattacharjee, A. & Das, A. (2024). Adaptive and Inclusive Physical Education for Students with Special Needs. *International Journal of Social Impact*, 9(1), 12-20. DIP: 18.02.002/20240901, DOI: 10.25215/2455/0901002
- Azzahra, I. M., Diana, R.R., Nirwana, S. E., Wiranta, S. R., Andriani, M. K. (2022). Learning facilities and infrastructure based on the characteristics of Children with Special Needs in inclusive education. *Al-Athfaal: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 5 (2), 169-190 <http://ejournal.radenintan.ac.id/index.php/al-athfaal>.
- Bolourian, Y., Losh, A., Hamsho, N., Eisenhower, A., & Blacher, J. (2022). General Education Teachers' Perceptions of Autism, Inclusive Practices, and Relationship Building Strategies. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 52(9), 3977–3990. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-021-05266-4>
- Haug, P. (2017). Understanding inclusive education: ideals and reality. *Scandinavian Journal of Disability Research*, 19(3), 206–217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15017419.2016.1224778>
- Kanmani, T. “Assistive and Adaptative Devices in Inclusive Education.” (2023) Shanlax *International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, 11, no. S1, 2023, pp. 120–23. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34293/sijash.v11iS1i2-Nov.7330>
- Khan, I. K., & Behlo, M. G. (2014). Inclusive Education at Primary Level: Reality or Phantasm. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 1 (1), 1-19
- Pravash, K.M.& Vaishali (2022). Inclusive Education: Infrastructural Facilities for CWSN in Delhi. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.25215/21101.068>.
- Mangal, S. K. (2019). *Educating Exceptional Children; An introduction to Special Education*: PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd Delhi-110092
- Simorangkir, R. R. M. (2021). Inclusion School Education Facilities and Infrastructure. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention (IJHSSI)*. 10 (5) Ser. III (May 2021 p. 22-25) ISSN (Online): 2319 – 7722, ISSN (Print): 2319 – 7714 www.ijhssi.org
- Thomas, F. B. (2022). The Role of Purposive Sampling Technique as a Tool for Informal Choices in a Social Sciences in *Research Methods*.